

Supplementary material. Codebook

Own elaboration. Source: Exported file from the content analysis of the videos, conducted using Atlas.ti (v.24.0).

Categories (management styles)	Definition	Examples of coded quotes
AVOIDANCE	Denying the existence of conflict, avoiding it or avoiding certain issues; making non-committal and/or irrelevant statements, etc. (e.g. making a joke, not commenting, not talking about the issue, etc.).	(Scenario 1). Good morning, everybody. I'm JC, I'm going to be your Art and Visual Education teacher this year. First of all, I would like to ask you: what is art for you? How did you enjoy this subject in your previous years at school? This year it's going to be (...) (a student says, "what a lot of bullshit"). Oops, I'm stuck, what a shock! (the participant addresses the researchers, sighs and continues). Well, is there anyone who agrees with your classmate? No one? Heh heh... she's all alone. But look, it's okay to say this is bullshit. In fact, there is an artist, whose name I can't remember, who made the artwork 'Artist's Shit', during the artistic avant-garde of the 20th century. We will study it later in the year. Now let's start with art from a few years earlier [D3.0:15:1:33., P9_Visual Arts].
COLLABORATION (INTEGRATING)	Open communication to explore disagreement, identify underlying concerns and seek alternatives that meet the interests of each party (e.g. clarify situations by listening to the learner, asking additional questions...).	(scenario 1). Hello, good morning. Today we will start a lesson on Aristotle and we will analyse the political texts based on which we will work on the whole theme of anthropology, of the human being. We are going to work hard, above all, on (the question) what is for Aristotle the human being and his position in society (interruption, a student shouts: asshole!) Excuse me, David, please, can you come over here (the student doesn't react, the participant insists). David, you have to come over here, please (she raises her voice) David, please, can you get up and stand over here next to me? He looks at the whole class and repeats: Please, you have to get up, come here (the pupil approaches the teacher). David, what's wrong? what's going on? why did you make that comment? (the pupil doesn't react, she laughs nervously, the practice is cut short) (D: 18:2 17s_P18_Philosophy)
ACCOMMODATION/ INDULGING	The accommodating mode, unlike domination, is not assertive, but cooperative. This behaviour may mean 'splitting the difference',	(scenario 1) Good afternoon, everyone. We will continue the history lesson we started yesterday. Today we are going to talk about al-Andalus. Yesterday we saw that, before them, there were the Visigoths and today it is time to get into them (al-Andalus). The period of al-Andalus corresponds to the 8th century

	<p>exchanging concessions, or attempting a quick compromise. The accommodator puts aside his or her own interests to satisfy those of the other person. There is an element of self-sacrifice in this mode (e.g. the teacher may be generous or altruistic, accepting the student's demands to avoid confrontation, when he/she would prefer not to do so).</p>	<p>until the end of the 15th century (...) (A STUDENT SHOUTS: what a load of bullshit!)... Eehh, uhmm... that's not on the syllabus, OK? (the class laughs). Who was it? (facing the class, she asks) Was it you, Daniel? What's wrong with you? (she looks at the whole class with expectant eyes, waiting for an answer, which doesn't come). Well, can you repeat the joke so we can all laugh? I can't hear you, what were you saying? OK, I see it had nothing to do with the class, I'll continue with my explanation. Well, as I was saying, (there's a commotion). Kids, please, I'm talking. You can talk during the break if you feel like it (she pauses and sighs: Ufff! the practice stops) (D22:2 27s_P6 Geography and History)</p>
<p>COMPROMISE/ GIVING IN/</p>	<p>Discussing and debating issues and problems with the pupil and/or the whole class to explore possible new solutions and ways of addressing perceived relational difficulties (e.g. telling a pupil that you will talk to them after class)</p>	<p>(scenario 1) Today we will have a class on volume, in visual arts (nervous laughter) and I suggest we do a class experiment with recycled materials and from there we are going to generate a volume (A STUDENT SHOUTS SOMETHING IMPROPER). Hey, but, well, what was that for? What exactly was that for? What was that for, Damián? (the participant asks, approaching the student) Won't you answer? Nobody was amused by what you said. We're going to talk about this when the class is over. (he/she stops the class and speaks to the researchers: do I have to continue with the class? (D1:6 10s, P1-Visual Arts)</p>
<p>DOMINANCE/ /AUTHORITARIAN</p>	<p>Seeks to satisfy their own interests at the expense of those of the other person, using whatever means they see fit to ensure that their position wins. Defending one's own rights, defending a position one believes to be correct, or simply trying to win.</p>	<p>(scenario 3) Today we are going to do group work, so we will split into groups, you are already split (as per the usual classroom arrangement), let's see four, four, eight. OK. We can use this, as the groups four and four, and well, I see, not much parity, really (a student gets up from his seat, the participant produces a 'nervous laugh') But, well, are you going to another group, ah, no, you're going out through the window (nervous laugh). Please, sit back down, please (authoritarian tone) you are disrespecting your classmates (I don't know what to say to this man, because he has perched himself there at the window). I'm sorry, in this situation I don't know what to do – the participant says this as if thinking out loud) (D1:13 2m 34s_P1_Visual Arts)</p>

Source of definitions: Thomas, K. W. (2008). Thomas-Kilmann conflict mode. *TKI Profile and Interpretive Report*, 1(11). <https://lig360.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Conflict-Styles-Assessment.pdf>